

INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF MICROWAVE CURING UPON THE MICROMECHANICS OF KEVLAR/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

It is usual to cure thermoset matrix composites in conventional convection ovens. Microwave curing offers the advantage of great improvements in the speed of cure. Microwave radiation is used in a growing number of commercial applications in the processing of materials. The effect of such a process upon the micromechanics of composites is not yet well established. This paper seeks to improve upon the present knowledge by using Raman spectroscopy to measure directly the critical length in composites prepared using conventional and microwave heating routes. The interfacial shear stress distributions at a number of levels of loading was also obtained and hence the interfacial shear strength. It was found that the interfacial shear strength was higher in samples which had been post-cured using microwave radiation than in conventionally cured materials. The critical lengths were similar.

INTRODUCTION

Conventionally thermoset resins are cured using convection ovens. This has a serious drawback in that because of the slow thermal transport through the resin the curing time is normally long, perhaps of the order of hours. For some time in industry microwave radiation has been used to process materials because it is much faster. There has been little detailed investigation of the effect of microwave curing upon the fibre/matrix interface and the micromechanical properties of composites, however. In this paper the effect of the method of curing on the micromechanics of a Kevlar/epoxy system will be explored.

Several researchers have investigated the use of microwaves in order to cure epoxy-based composite systems[1-9]. The microwave radiation penetrates the whole sample at once so that the curing time is much shorter than for conventionally cured materials[7-10]. There is some dispute in the literature concerning the effect of microwave radiation upon the rate of reaction for epoxies[5,6,11]. At the present three types of microwave heating system are used, namely tunable single mode resonant cavities[2,10], multimode ovens[3] and waveguides[9]. Of these the single mode, tunable cavities have great efficiency, but multimode ovens, being domestic microwaves, are easiest to obtain. In this work a commercial multimode microwave oven was used.

Boey and Lee [8] have cured a glass/epoxy system using both conventional and microwave heating. They found that the flexural strength of the microwave heated system was as high as for the conventionally cured material and that the flexural modulus was significantly higher. Some work has been done on the interfacial properties of microwave and thermally cured glass/epoxy composites[7]. Compression lap shear tests and pull-out tests were used in order to measure the average frictional shear strength and the interfacial shear strength of the composites. They found that the average frictional shear strength of the specimens cured using microwave radiation was twice that of those which were thermally cured.

There are several approaches to measuring the interfacial shear strength of composites. These include the fragmentation[12-13], pull-out[14-17] and microbond tests[18-20]. These tests have the disadvantage that they give different results even when applied to the same fibre/matrix system. Recently Raman spectroscopy has been used to examine in detail the micromechanics of composites and has been found to be a very powerful technique[21]. In this work Raman spectroscopy will be used to measure the critical length in and interfacial shear strength of a Kevlar/epoxy system after conventional thermal post-curing and microwave post-curing. Thus it will be possible to make direct comparisons of the interfacial properties which each curing method yields without the difficulties associated with the usual micromechanical tests.

EXPERIMENTAL

In this work Kevlar 49 fibres and a Ciba Geigy epoxy resin (Araldite LY5052/HY5052) were used. The resin was mixed in the recommended ratio of 100:38 parts by weight. The mixture was degassed in a vacuum oven for twenty minutes, stirred, then degassed for a further thirty minutes. Samples with and without short fibres in them were prepared. For samples of the matrix alone the resin was poured into a mould 150x150x5mm and allowed to cure at room temperature. The specimens containing single fibres were fabricated by pouring epoxy resin into the mould to a thickness of approximately 2mm. This was allowed to gel at room temperature. Single fibres of Kevlar, 3mm in length, were then placed on the surface and more resin poured on top. The total thickness of the sample was 4mm.

Post-curing was achieved using both conventional thermal and microwave heating. For the later a domestic microwave oven with an operating frequency of 2.45 GHz and power of 1kw was employed. Initially a small strip of resin, approximately 20 grammes in weight, was placed in the centre of the oven. On heating this it was found that there was rapid degradation of the sample and the curing was not uniform. Hot spots were found in the centre of the oven and at intervals radially outwards from it. Subsequent samples were positioned so that curing was uniform. Four samples, of total mass 65 grammes, were placed in the oven at a time and in the centre of the oven was a beaker containing 300 ml of water initially at a temperature of 1-2 °C. The water absorbed a large part of the microwave energy. Similar difficulties with microwave curing have been encountered by other workers[12]. After post-curing the extent of cure was found using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The time for full cure was found to be 220 seconds.

For the thermally post-cured samples the specimens were placed in a conventional oven at 100 °C and 200 °C for different periods of time. The degree of curing was again ascertained by DSC. The post-curing time found for samples at 100 °C was found to be 1 hour and for those at 200 °C was ten minutes. Some samples were also left at room temperature for seven days.

Some samples were also made by dipping single fibres in a solution of epoxy in ethanol. The coated fibre was left for the resin to gel for 4 hours and then post-cured in the microwave

oven. These coated samples were then embedded in epoxy as described above and the resin was allowed to cure for 7 days at room temperature.

RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

Raman spectroscopy was used to examine the micromechanics of the single fibre composites. The system used consisted of a Spex 1000M single monochromator coupled to a modified Olympus BH-2 optical microscope. Additional laser line rejection was provided by a colloidal filter placed close to the slits of the spectrometer. The spectra were excited using a 10 mw HeNe laser operating at 632.8 nm and collected using a Wright Instruments charge coupled device camera. The laser beam was always polarised parallel to the fibre axis.

Single fibres were tested using a device in which the fibre was fastened at either end to an aluminium block with cyanoacrylate adhesive using aluminium foil end tabs. One of these blocks could be displaced by means of a micrometer so that the strain in the sample was known. Thus the rate of change in Raman frequency which strain for these fibres could be checked. The single fibre composites were strained using a Polymer Laboratories Minimat which was fastened to the stage of the microscope. An electrical strain gauge was glued to the surface of the sample and the resistance of this measured using a digital multimeter. Raman spectra were taken along the fibre at different strain levels until the sample failed or the fibre began to fragment. The spectra were analysed by fitting a quadratic function to the background and a Lorenzian function to the Raman peak using the Levenburg-Marquardt algorithm. Once the peak positions had been established these were converted into strain using the rate of change of Raman band position with strain measured for the single fibres in air. Plots of strain in the fibre as a function of position along the fibre could thus be obtained. These were converted to interfacial shear stress distributions using the well known expression

$$\tau_x = \frac{E_f d}{4} \left\{ \frac{de_f}{dx} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where τ_x is the interfacial shear stress, E_f is the fibre Young's modulus, d is the fibre diameter and de_f/dx is the slope of the strain against distance curve.

RESULTS

SINGLE FIBRE CALIBRATION

The rate of shift of the 1610 cm^{-1} band with strain of the Kevlar fibre was measured for a number of gauge lengths to see if there this had any effect. Gauge lengths of 20, 50, 100 and 200 mm were used. The results are summarised in Table 1. A linear regression function was used to fit to the plot and the mean gradient of all gauge lengths was found to be $-4.08 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$. This is in good agreement with previous studies [22]. The graphs of Raman frequency versus strain are used as the Raman frequency calibration curves for converting Raman frequency into fibre strain during testing of the model composites.

Table 1

Gauge length (mm)	20	50	100	200
Raman band shift with strain (cm ⁻¹ /%)	-4.20	-3.96	-4.07	-3.93

SINGLE FIBRE COMPOSITES

Interfacial shear stress distributions were measured for specimens and these corresponded in general to those expected from the Cox model. The samples which were cured using microwaves and the conventional oven had a fair amount of shrinkage resulting in compressive strains in the fibres when there was no applied stress. For this reason it was found that the fibre strain was less than that in the matrix. The critical length was measured in each of the specimens and the results are summarised in Figure 1. Due to the difficulty in deciding when the strain in the fibre has reached a plateau value the distance at which the strain in the fibre becomes 0.9 of the plateau value ($0.9e_{\text{fmax}}$) is given. The figure shows that in general the critical length is longer for the samples cured at room temperature than for the other samples. The critical lengths for the microwave post-cured samples are of the same order as those for the thermal post-cured materials.

Interfacial shear stress (ISS) distributions were derived for each type of sample. An example is shown in figure 2. This is the ISS for a specimen which contained a single fibre which had been dipped in a solution of epoxy resin in ethanol and then post-cured in a microwave oven before being embedded in more epoxy matrix.

Table 2 lists the results for the maximum interfacial shear stress recorded for composites post-cured under different conditions. In all of the samples tested the interfacial bonding was good. It can be seen that room temperature cure an interfacial shear strength of 40 MPa was obtained. This is consistent with previous work on this resin/ fibre system. At the higher cure temperatures the interfacial shear strength is improved and the samples now show interfacial shear strengths of the order of 50 MPa. Finally the samples which have been microwave cured exhibit better interfacial shear strengths with both samples tested giving values of 60 MPa. The samples where the resin is first coated on the fibre and then microwave cured show high values of interfacial shear strength. On inspection in the scanning electron microscope these samples were found to have a non-uniform coating of resin on the fibre.

Table 2. Interfacial shear strengths obtained for different curing conditions

Curing condition	
Room temperature cure	40 MPa
Thermal cure at 100°C	51 MPa
Thermal cure at 200°C	47 MPa
Microwave cure	60 MPa
Surface coated fibre	66 MPa

Figure 1 - Plot of critical length with maximum fibre strain under different curing conditions.

Figure 2. Interfacial shear stress in a composite containing a single fibre which was coated in a solution of epoxy resin in ethanol and microwave cured

CONCLUSIONS

Microwave processing of composites offers great potential for obtaining large improvements in the cycle time. It has been shown that not only is there a speed advantage to microwave processing but the interfacial properties of the composites are not hindered. Indeed the data presented here shows the microwave processing can lead to better interfacial shear strengths. It is clear that if the route of pre-coating the fibres with resin and then microwave post-curing these is to be used then a more dilute epoxy solution should be used.

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